

Synthesis of New Local Anaesthetics. Part V

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2, 6-Diphenyl-, 2, 6-dicinnamyl-, 2, 6-difurfuryl-, 2, 6-dianisyl-, 2, 6-di-*p*-dimethylaminophenyl-, 2, 6-di-*p*-tolyl- and 2, 6-dipiperonyl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-piperidonoacetyl-2'-amino-4'-phenylthiazoles and their hydrochlorides have been synthesised and their local anaesthetic activities tested. The hydrochlorides of 2, 6-dianisyl-, 2, 6-difurfuryl-, and 2, 6-diphenyl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-piperidonoacetyl-2'-amino-4'-phenylthiazoles have been found to be active.

In continuation of the previous work on local anaesthetics by Bhargava *et al.* (this *Journal*, 1957, **34**, 42; 1960, **37**, 241, 314; 1961, **38**, 77) it was considered worthwhile to prepare 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole and to condense it first with chloroacetyl chloride and subsequently with 2,6-diphenyl-, 2,6-dicinnamyl-, 2,6-difurfuryl-, 2, 6-dianisyl-, 2, 6-di-*p*-dimethylaminophenyl-, 2,6-di-*p*-tolyl-, and 2,6-dipiperonyl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-piperidone so as to obtain the corresponding 2'-amino-4'-phenylthiazoles. The hydrochlorides of these bases have been prepared and their local anaesthetic activity has been tested by frog's sciatic plexus method.

Pharmacological screening, according to the procedure adopted by Bulbring and Wajda (*J. Pharmacol.*, 1945, **85**, 78), has shown that the hydrochlorides of 2,6-dianisyl-, 2,6-difurfuryl-, and 2,6-diphenyl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-piperidonoacetyl-2'-amino-4'-phenylthiazoles are strongly active compounds. All these compounds with the exception of 2,6-dicinnamyl derivative take less time for the onset of anaesthesia than procaine hydrochloride, the standard substance.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chloroacetyl-2-amino-4-phenylthiazole.—Chloroacetyl chloride (3 c.c.), dissolved in dry benzene (12 c.c.), was gradually added to 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole (Dodson and King, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2242) (5 g.), dissolved in benzene (30 c.c.). The reaction mixture was warmed at 70° on a water bath for 1.5 hours. Benzene was distilled; the residue was washed first with sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water, and dried. The product was crystallised from ethanol in light yellow crystals, m.p. 157°, yield 19 g. (Found: S, 12.72. $C_{11}H_9ON_2ClS$ requires S, 12.63%).

2,6-Diaryl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-piperidones.—A mixture of ethyl acetoacetate (4 c.c.), benzaldehyde (4 c.c.), and ammonium acetate (2.3 g.) in glacial acetic acid (15 c.c.) was heated under reflux at 110° in an oil bath for 2.5 hours. The contents were cooled and dissolved in ether; a current of dry HCl gas was passed into it for 15 minutes. The hydrochloride so formed was dissolved in methanol and decomposed with ammonia (conc.) at 0° to precipitate the free base, which was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 106°. (Found: N, 4.30. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{21}O_3N$: N, 4.33%).

Similarly other piperidones were prepared (see Table I).

TABLE I

No.	Aldehyde.	Yield.	Colour.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Calc.
1.	Benzaldehyde	40%	Yellow	106°	$C_{20}H_{21}O_3N$	4.30	4.33
2.	Cinnamaldehyde	87	Brown	112°	$C_{24}H_{25}O_3N$	3.85	3.73
3.	Furfural	85	Violet	105°	$C_{19}H_{17}O_3N$	4.64	4.61
4.	Anisaldehyde	84	Brown	88°	$C_{23}H_{25}O_3N$	3.63	3.65
5.	<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino-benzaldehyde	92	Do	118°	$C_{26}H_{27}O_3N$	10.21	10.26
6.	<i>p</i> -Tolualdehyde	78	Yellow	135°	$C_{23}H_{25}O_3N$	3.99	3.98
7.	Piperonal	68	Brown	125°	$C_{22}H_{23}O_3N$	3.36	3.39

2,6-Diphenyl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-piperidonoacetyl-2'-amino-4'-phenylthiazole.—To chloroacetyl-2-amino-4-phenylthiazole (1.25 g.), dissolved in ethanol (15 c.c.), 2,6-diphenyl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-piperidone (1.6 g.) was added; the mixture was refluxed for 4.5 hours on a water bath. Excess of alcohol was recovered by distillation; the residue was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and finally with water. The product was crystallised from benzene in brown crystals, m.p. 125°. (Found: S, 6.04. $C_{31}H_{29}O_4N_3S$ requires S, 5.93%).

Similarly other 2,6-diaryl-4'-phenylthiazoles were prepared. Their hydrochlorides were also obtained as usual and crystallised from acetone (see Table II).

TABLE II

No. *DPT.	Yield.	M.P.	Aminophenylthiazoles.		Hydrochlorides.		
			Formula.	% Sulphur. Found. Calc.	M.P.	% Chlorine. Found. Calc.	
1.	90%	125°	$C_{31}H_{29}O_4N_3S$	6.04 5.93	111°	6.16 6.11	
2.	85	119°	$C_{28}H_{25}O_4N_3S$	5.38 5.41	104°	5.69 5.65	
3.	77	128°	$C_{27}H_{25}O_4N_3S$	6.20 6.16	122°	6.32 6.39	
4.	84	117°	$C_{33}H_{33}O_4N_3S$	5.30 5.34	101°	5.42 5.53	
5.	96	193°	$C_{28}H_{29}O_4N_3S$	4.89 5.11	94°	
6.	88	121°	$C_{29}H_{25}O_4N_3S$	5.60 5.64	95°	5.80 5.88	
7.	93	123°	$C_{32}H_{29}O_4N_3S$	5.29 5.10	96°	5.28 5.34	

* DPT stands for 2, 6-diaryl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-piperidonoacetyl-2'-amino-4'-phenylthiazole, corresponding to compounds in Table I.

Pharmacological Test: Plexus Anaesthesia in Frogs.—Hydrochloride solutions of 0.1% and 0.2% were used and the time of onset of anaesthesia was recorded and compared with that of procaine hydrochloride as a standard substance. The results are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

No. DPT hydrochloride	0.1 % Solution for onset of anaesthesia for		0.2 % Solution for onset of anaesthesia for	
	0.05N-HCl	0.1N-HCl.	0.05N-HCl.	0.1N-HCl
1.	7 mins.	10 mins.	5 mins.	9 mins.
2.	14	16	12	15
3.	6	9	5	8
4.	4	6	3	5
6.	10	12	8	10
7.	11	14	9	12
8. Procaine hydrochloride	10	15	8	14

Pharmacological screening shows that hydrochlorides of 2,6-dianisyl-, 2,6-difurfuryl-, and 2,6-diphenyl derivatives are active as local anaesthetics and require less time for onset of anaesthesia than the standard substance, procaine hydrochloride.

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